

This document includes the Supplementary Material (annex 1 to 6) of the manuscript published in Open Research Europe of Depellegrin et al. 2024 entitled: *Addressing ocean planning challenges in a highly crowded sea space: a case study for the regional sea of Catalonia (Western Mediterranean)*. All the references to this document can be found in Depellegrin et al. 2024.

Supplementary material

Annex 1. Blue Economy settings and geospatial data sources

Blue Economy settings: Numerous Blue Economy activities co-exist in the study area. Together with the Canary Islands and the Adriatic Sea, Catalonia belongs to the most visited coastal areas by holidaymakers (Blue Economy Report, 2021). There are 44 marinas as proxy for the sector and its spatial demands. Total number of berths is $n = 32993$ (PdG, 2023). Underwater Cultural Heritage sites are represented by 10 shipwrecks (PADI, 2023) at about 60 to 10 meter depth located in coastal areas of the Costa Brava (e.g. the ferry *Reggio Messina* sunken in 1991 or the tugboat *Boreas* sunken in 1982) and Costa Daurada (e.g. the wooden fish boat *Vapor del Miracle*) in proximity of Tarragona. The shipwrecks are no-days popular artificial reefs for recreational and professional divers (Palamós Dive Centre, 2023; Divingaway, 2023; Buceaenlahistoria, 2023). In addition, from 1967 to 2003 about 60 artificial reefs were installed functioning as biodiversity production sites and or protection against illegal fishery activities (GenCat, 2022a). The oil and gas sector includes the *Casablanca* platform and oil field (Repsol, 2009), Spain's biggest oil field in operation since 1982. The platform is located 44 km off the coast and connected via a 59 km pipeline to the port of Tarragona. The platform is reaching its end-of-life and will be decommissioned by 2028 (CatalanNews, 2021). In addition there are 158 exploration wells that have been installed since the 1960s. In the study area there is one active licensing site for exploitation located in front of the Ebro Continental Shelf (approx. 1763 km²). There are 32 protected areas including international sites, such as Natura2000 sites (13 SPA - Special Protected Areas under the EU Bird Directive; 11 SCI - Sites of Community Importance under the EU Habitat Directive); 3 Specially Protected Area of Mediterranean Importance (SPAMI; Racspa, 2022) and 6 national sites (3 nature reserves; 1 marine protected area; 1 natural park and 1 protection plan). Commercial fishery is one of the most important industrial sectors of the region (ICATMAR, 20). There are 20 first fish landing ports (EMODNet, 2022) and over 700 professional coastal fishing vessels (GenCat, 2021). Bottom trawling of demersal species (red mullet, European hake, deep-water rose shrimp, Norway lobster, and blue and red shrimp) is the most important fishery modality with a revenue of 95.86 M€ in 2021 (ICATMAR, 2021). Aquaculture is an important complement to commercial fishery in Spain (Apromar, 2020; Bacher *et al.*, 2014). According to EMODnet data (accessed 01/2023) there are 10 aquaculture production sites in the region farming European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), Gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and Tuna (*Thunus spp.*). Mollusc aquaculture refers to Oysters (*Ostrea edulis* and *Crassostrea gigas*; Carrasco Querol *et al.*, 2017) and Japanese Carpet Shell (*Ruditapes philippinarum*; GenCat, 2022b). The regional freshwater-marine aquaculture industry has an annual revenue of 239 million € and creates 1250 jobs (Prodeca, 2023). There are 13 industrial ports in the region (EMODNet Geoviewer, 2023). The port of Barcelona is a major maritime transport hub for Europe and for the Mediterranean (UfM, 2021; Osés *et al.*, 2021). In 2021 the total traffic of tons from maritime transportation vectors reached 66 million tons (PdB, 2021).

Annex 2. Regional MSP database for the region of Catalonia

Annex 3. Distribution of fishing effort and presence of protected areas in form of PUA Biodiversity.

Annex 4. Distribution of marinas including number of berths and distribution of protected areas as PUA – Biodiversity.

Annex 5. a) Spatial contribution of the three sea zoning types to the protection of 30% of sea areas. b) All PUA for biodiversity corresponding to existing protected areas fulfil the 30% target. Future HPA Biodiversity sites would further increase protection level. c) Marine protection as function of distance from shoreline in nautical miles (nm). Note: dotted line indicates Biodiversity Strategy 2030 target of 30% of sea space protection. *Note:* HPA are approximate areas.

Current (PUA) and potential future (HPA) regional contribution to Biodiversity Strategy 2030 of the Catalan sea space

b) Regional contribution (in %) of PUA and HPA sites

c) Contribution (in %) according coastal distance gradient

Annex 6. Regional Offshore wind energy potentials in Catalonia. Floating offshore wind energy potentials are defined according GWEC dataset. There are two subregions of the study area that show suitability for the floating OWE deployment: Subregion 1: Northern Catalonia from Palamós to French boarder; Subregion 2: Southern Catalonia from Cambrils to northern section of Ebro Delta.

